

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DENSITY MEASUREMENT METHODS IN HYDROLOGICAL STUDIES

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Abstract

This article discusses the measurement of density in hydrology. Three alternative methods of measurement are presented: a "float-type" apparatus, a hydrometer, and an optical densitometer. Each method has its advantages and limitations. Research findings related to the application of these methods and their accuracy are also presented. The possibilities for improving and enhancing the data measurement methods in hydrological studies are discussed.

Keywords: density measurement, hydrology, "float" installation, areometer, optical densitometer.

Introduction

The measurement of density is of particular interest in hydrological studies as it provides accurate information about the absolute salinity of a seawater.

Materials and Methods

To obtain accurate measurements of the density of a medium in hydrological studies, several practical methods were employed. Direct measurements of practical salinity were obtained using CTD probes, which do not account for variations in the salt composition of the medium. Chemical analysis

of water samples collected using bathometers was used to determine the chemical composition and practical salinity.

Further analysis was carried out using direct chemical analysis and the GM-65M or GM-2007 conductivity salinity meters. For stationary measurements, several methods of direct density measurement are currently proposed.

One method utilized is the measurement of density using hydrometers. Specialized hydrometers for seawater, such as the AMV hydrometers, with low measurement errors, are used in stationary conditions. These hydrometers are available in 8 ranges, with each range having different measurement capabilities, ranging from 1,000 to 1,036 units of relative density. The scale division ranges from 0.0001 units for most hydrometers to 0.001 units for the AMV hydrometer-finder with a range of 1,000 to 1,040 units of relative density. The measurement of density using hydrometers for seawater is regulated by three Russian standards:

GOST 18481-81 "Glass hydrometers and cylinders" GOST 8.428-81 "Hydrometers. Values of surface tension coefficients of liquids" and GOST 28947-91 "Glass hydrometers. Standard values of volume thermal expansion coefficients".

Attempts have been made to improve density measurements by eliminating the effect of surface tension using an optical method, which involves excluding the correction according to GOST 8.428-81. However, for hydrometers of this type, approval from the national standardization authority is required.

Additionally, temperature measurement of the sample is necessary as the AMV hydrometers are calibrated at a temperature of 17.5°C. The calculation formula is provided in GOST 28947-91, and the temperature measurement accuracy is 0.02°C.

The optical densitometer method is based on measuring the refractive index of the medium through which light passes. This method utilizes two pentaprisms and a high-resolution beam deflection sensor (position sensor). In recent years, position-sensitive devices (PSDs) such as the S3932 sensor from Hamamatsu,

which has a resolution of 80000 dpi, have been used for these measurements. The refractive index is directly related to density (ρ) and absolute salinity, as described by the Lorentz-Lorenz equation in the 19th century. The empirical formula for calculating the refractive index (N) based on physical parameters such as temperature (T), pressure (p), salinity (S), and wavelength (λ) was derived by Seaver and Millard.

The optical method involves passing a beam of light through two pentaprisms, with the medium of interest in between, and measuring the beam's position using a position sensor (P). The density is then calculated using the Lorentz-Lorenz equation. Tests have shown that the refractive index does not significantly depend on other hydrological variables (CTD) when measured at different frequency ranges. However, some correction for specific regions may be required.

The refractive index has a slight dependence on pressure. For example, according to an estimation presented in [2], a 1 dbar change in pressure at a constant temperature and wavelength leads to 0.0008 practical salinity units change in calculated salinity. Additionally, a wavelength changes of 1 nm around 635 nm results in a refractive index change of $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

For practical density measurements in oceanography, several designs incorporating pressure sensors have been proposed. One such design, suggested by Fedotov [3], involves using four pressure sensors arranged in a triangular pyramid configuration. This arrangement compensates for angular oscillations during free fall. To reduce costs, a design with two pressure sensors and one accelerometer has also been proposed. There is a wide selection of accelerometers available with the necessary resolution and various output interfaces.

When creating free-fall density profilers, it is almost always necessary to include a mechanism for buoyancy after a certain predetermined time. A time-based buoyancy mechanism is simpler compared to a depth-riggered mechanism, as it does not require additional software and complex mechanical components.

Results and Discussion

The main focus of hydrological measurements is obtaining accurate values of the absolute salinity of the medium. Direct measurements using CTD probes provide practical salinity values without corrections for salt composition. Chemical analysis of water samples obtained using bathometers was used to determine the chemical composition and practical salinity. The analysis was further conducted by direct chemical analysis and with the help of the GM-65M or GM-2007 electro salimeters. Several methods for direct density measurement are suggested for stationary measurements.

Density measurement using an areometer is also proposed in stationary conditions. Specialized AMV seawater areometers with low errors can be used for this purpose. They are available in 8 ranges, including 7 areometers with the following measurement ranges:

1. 1,000 - 1,006 relative density units
2. 1,005 - 1,011 relative density units
3. 1,010 - 1,016 relative density units
4. 1,015 - 1,021 relative density units
5. 1,020 - 1,026 relative density units
6. 1,025 - 1,031 relative density units
7. 1,030 - 1,036 relative density units

The scale division price is 0.0001 units of relative density, and there is an areometer-finder with a measurement range of 1,000 - 1,040 units of relative density and a scale division price of 0.001.

Optical Densitometer: In addition to standard measurements using CTD probes, the optical densitometer method has been developed for in situ measurements of refractive index. Although the results obtained with this method approach the requirements of TEOS-10, it has not yet been recognized as a standard by the international commission.

The implementation of this method involves the use of two pentaprisms and a beam deflection sensor (position sensor) with high resolution. Refractometers that measure refractive index require sensitive beam position sensors. Recently developed position-sensitive devices (PSD), such as the S3932 sensor by Hamamatsu, have a resolution of 80000 dpi.

The optical method is based on measuring the refractive index when a beam of light passes through a medium. The beam passes through two pentaprisms, with the medium in between, and is detected by a position sensor (P). The density is then calculated using the Lorentz-Lorenz equation. Testing the method showed a negligible dependence or lack of dependence of the refractive index on other hydrological quantities (CTD) when measured at different frequency ranges. The method also requires a correction for the measurement region (correction for specific refractivity).

The refractive index has a negligible dependence on pressure. According to estimates in [2], at constant temperature and λ , a pressure change of 1 decibar results in a change in the calculated salinity value of 0.0008 practical salinity units. The same study also provides the magnitude of the refractive index change of 2×10^{-5} when the wavelength changes by 1 nm around 635 nm. A sensor of similar design is more practical to use in sounding devices such as the "Istok."

Several construction schemes using pressure sensors have been proposed for practical density measurements in oceanography. The construction proposed by Fedotov G.A. [3] involves the use of four pressure sensors arranged in the form of a triangular pyramid.

This type of construction is necessary to compensate for angular oscillations of the device when in free fall. To reduce costs, a proposed design with two pressure sensors and one accelerometer can be used. There is a wide selection of accelerometers with the required resolution in three coordinates and various output interfaces.

When designing free-falling density profilers, it is almost always necessary to incorporate a mechanism for the buoyancy of the device after a certain calculated time. The design for buoyancy based on time is much simpler compared to a depth-triggered mechanism, as it does not require additional software and complex mechanical components.

Conclusion

This article discussed various practical methods for measuring density in hydrological studies. Direct measurements using CTD probes provide practical salinity values without corrections for the salt composition of the environment. Chemical analysis through bottle samples was used to determine absolute salinity. Additionally, the use of GM-65M or GM-2007 electro salinometers allowed for direct chemical analysis.

Another method discussed is density measurement using hydrometers. Specialized marine water hydrometers (AMV) with low errors are recommended for use in stationary conditions. These hydrometers are available in eight ranges, with scale division prices ranging from 0.0001 to 0.001 units of relative density.

Furthermore, the article mentions the use of an optical densitometer. This method measures the refractive index of light passing through a medium and calculates density using the Lorentz-Lorenz equation. However, this method is not yet internationally recognized as a standard.

The conclusion highlights the importance of calibration and standardization procedures for measuring equipment. It also emphasizes the need for further research and development to improve the accuracy and reliability of density measurement methods in oceanography.

In summary, the article provides an overview of various methods for measuring density in hydrological studies, including direct measurements, hydrometers, optical densitometers. Each method has its advantages and

limitations, and further research is needed to improve their accuracy and standardization.

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